

Is Zhihu mention to academic papers useful for altmetrics studies?

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Introduction

Academic papers are used in many ways. Altmetrics is especially useful in revealing how academic papers are applied outside the scholarly community. For example, policy document mentions and news mentions can reflect the societal impact of academic papers (Wooldridge & King, 2019). Twitter mentions and Facebook mentions are useful in reflecting the public attention (Cui, Fang, & Wang, 2021). F1000 rating and online syllabus can indicate the educational impact. In comparison, Q&A platforms have been seldom explored. Q&A platforms are used to communicate knowledge surrounding various types of questions from daily life to focused topics. They are potentially relevant in revealing how academic papers are used to improve public users' knowledge about many topics.

Zhihu (zhihu.com) is an extremely popular Q&A platform in China, similar to Quora. It is valued for its high-quality answers and a pioneer for payment-based Q&A. Liu and Sun (2022) conducted a case study on machine learning topic and manually identified Zhihu mentions to academic papers. This study investigates Zhihu as a potential useful altmetrics source in China. It would contribute to altmetrics studies in twofold. It draws attention to the study of Q&A platforms and complements the global view with presenting an important local altmetrics source.

Methodology

Zhihu has organized questions and answers according to a hierarchy of topics. A question could simultaneously belong to several topics. A parent topic has several child topics, and the vice versa. For most disciplines, there are corresponding topics. Although it is not necessarily a strict disciplinary classification scheme, the scope of topic in general follows the discipline. Therefore, 5 representative topics were selected, each on behalf of a big category discipline. All 29 child topics under the 5 topics were included, each of them corresponding to a small category of discipline. For each child topic, all posts were collected via a self-coded program. From each post, mentions to academic papers were identified based on the DOI, URL and bibliographic information. For the mentioned academic papers, bibliographic data were collected from Web of Science.

Data about author of each post were also collected, including their location, occupation, gender, and account type. Data collection was conducted in June 2022. In total, 752,976 posts were collected of which 3,546 posts have mentioned 13,619 unique academic papers with 16,982 mentions.

Result

Coverage of Zhihu mentions in each discipline

The 5 first level disciplines are *Social Science, Technology and Application Science, Medical Science, Artificial Intelligence and Physics*. As shown in Table 1, in most child disciplines, percentage of posts with Zhihu mentions to academic papers remains at low level which is below 1%. However, for certain topics, the coverage is significantly high. For example, in *Federated learning*, the coverage is 10%.

Table 1. Coverage of Zhihu mentions to academic papers in each discipline

Second level topics	N.P.	P.M.
Economics	304,325	0.04%
Finance	55,148	0.09%
Linguistics	54,094	0.28%
Politics	47,211	0.08%
Pedagogy	45,668	0.04%
History	55,723	0.05%
Journalism and Communication	20,823	0.16%
Management Science	22,763	0.29%
Library and Information Science	7,379	0.20%
Law	215,215	0.01%
Engineering	41,794	0.16%
Materials Science	70,692	0.18%
Food Science	59,558	0.31%
Information Science	8,517	0.74%
Computing Science	4,780	0.80%
Preclinical Medicine	15,044	0.43%
Public Health and Epidemic Prevention Medicine	2,374	0.21%
Pattern Recognition	8,663	2.42%
Intelligent Robotics	9,040	0.32%
Automatic Driving	68,312	0.19%
Transfer Learning	3,418	8.89%
Machine Learning	63,639	1.46%
Federated Learning	1,840	10.1%
Nuclear Physics	19,781	0.26%
Polymer Physics	3,097	0.81%
Experimental Physics	9,671	0.50%
Applied Physics	3,000	0.03%
Quantum Physics	85,508	0.30%
Astrophysics	64,580	0.37%
Summary	752,976	0.47%

Note: N.P. is number of posts, P.M. is percentage of posts to academic papers

Immediacy of Zhihu mentions to academic papers

As shown in Figure 1, only 39% of Zhihu mentions occurred within 180 days after publication of academic paper. In contrast, 47% of Zhihu mentions were after 360 days of publication.

Figure 1. Immediacy distribution of Zhihu mentions to academic papers

Correlation between bibliographic characteristics of mentioned papers and number of Zhihu mentions

As shown in Table 2, number of citations is significantly and positively correlated with number of received Zhihu mentions, indicating that authors of posts that mention academic papers are likely to select authoritative and reliable papers to support their views.

Table 2. Correlation between number of Zhihu mentions and characteristics of mentioned papers

Characteristics	ρ
Length of paper title	-0.020*
Number of references	-0.011^
Altmetric attention score	0.099**
Number of citations	0.221**
Number of collaborative authors	0.018*
Number of collaborative affiliations	0.021^
Number of collaborative countries	0.033**
Number of fundings	0.000^
Number of source countries	0.028^

Note: * means $p < 0.05$, ** means $p < 0.01$, ^ means insignificance.

Characteristics of authors of Zhihu posts to academic papers

As shown in Figure 2, authors of Zhihu posts to academic papers are mainly located in China (81%), but are also scattered in 29 countries, for example, 10% of them are located in USA and 1.4% of them are located in UK.

Figure 2. Geographic distribution of authors of Zhihu posts to academic papers

As regards productivity, 70% of the authors have less than 3 posts to academic papers. However, the top 10 productive authors have contributed 22% of total mentions. As regards type of accounts, 93% of the authors are individual accounts, and have contributed to 87% of total Zhihu mentions. 85% of them are male. As regards industrial background, according to the occupation classification of Zhihu platform, 30% of the authors are occupied in high-tech industry, 12% of them are from the public service, 9% of them are from the education industry. They are followed by finance (2.6%) and medical service (1.8%).

Conclusions

Main conclusions are drawn as follows. (1) Coverage of Zhihu mentions to academic papers is 0.47%. For most investigated disciplines, the coverage is below 1%, however, for specific disciplines the coverage could be as high as 10%. (2) The immediacy of Zhihu mentions is weak, and 47% of them occurred after 360 days of publication. This suggests that author of Zhihu posts do not necessarily favour the newly published papers but rather prefer the highly cited reliable papers. The underlying reason could be that the authors aim to make their answer convincing by citing papers in their post. (3) The above conclusion is corroborated by that number of Zhihu mentions is significantly positively correlated with number of citations, while is weakly or not significantly correlated with other bibliographic characteristics. (4) Zhihu users with posts to academic papers are dominated by individual (93%) and male (85%). Most of them are lowly active but there are exceptions who frequently cite academic papers in the posts. These results indicate that Zhihu mention to academic papers may be used as evidence of impact of specific academic papers in a complementary way, for example, to serve as part of case studies of impact of a research output.

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